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THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGY IN CHILDREN WITH EPILEPSY AND THE IMPACT OF THE DISEASE IN THE DAILY LIVES OF THESE CHILDREN – PSYCHOLOGICAL THERAPY A SCREENING OBLIGATORY METHODS - OUR CLINICAL EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

Epilepsy represents the most common problem in pediatric neurology and greatly affects the health of these children, especially those cases where the prognosis is worse, so the assistance of psychologists and psychological therapy is mandatory screening method to these children. The aim of our study is how psychologist should make analysis of these children psychologically and they need to provide psychological support to these children and their families.

Key words: Psychologist, Children with Epilepsy, Psychological Therapy, Screening Methods.

Introduction

Any a disease which invades the child's health, especially those with serious prognosis in varying degrees affects children's attitude. Epilepsy to children has a special impact given on the one hand the nature of children, epileptic disease and on the other current attitudes that exist in our society. Epilepsy is one of the most common diseases in children neurological. Children with this type of disease exhibit emotional difficulties and behavioral problems those that are caused by harassment, ridicule and neglect that can be made these children with epilepsy independence in everyday living where they live with continued fear of next crisis.

The Aim

Aim of this study is the role of the psychologist in the analysis of children with epilepsy and psychological therapy.

Methodology

The study is retrospective and is carried out in January-June 2016 to hospitalized children in the Pediatric Clinic of the Department of Neuropediatric, children age was 9-14 years old, study includes 46 children 31 children were male while 15 children were female gender. The data of children were taken in the form of survey and questionnaire.

January – June	9 – 14 years old
46 children	
31 male	15 female

Results

Psychological therapy helps a lot these children in many aspects related to epilepsy. The focus of the therapy is how to tell children that what is epilepsy? Which is the kind of crisis that the child has, how to deal with epilepsy? What do we have to say to our friends about this kind of disease? How do help children do to a plan of dealing with this kind of disease? How to face ridicule? Psychological strategies are determined to understand the specific challenges of epilepsy to explore what do cause stress: to find ways to improve the compliance and to give recommendations on how to improve the quality of life.

Conclusion

The results obtained in our survey have contributed approximately 80% of patients can be helped significantly by supporting psychological therapy. Children with the daily difficulties can be minimized, if parents encourage positive approaches towards independence and, if they do not give importance more than should to unsuitability behavior. Counseling helps parents and children to face the disease in a positive way and by helping other children to work on the emotional issues associated with epilepsy.

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